

DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF CARBON/EPOXY QUASI-INTERWOVEN COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO LOW VELOCITY IMPACTS

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ABSTRACT

Robotic dry fibre placement (RDFP) is a preforming technology with the potential of mass-producing laminar composite preforms at the speed and quality required for the automotive and aerospace industries. The RDFP technology enables the placement on unidirectional (UD) fibres in arbitrary in-plane directions, producing a laminate with tailored mechanical properties. Due to the layered nature of these lay-ups, the resulting composites exhibit poor out-of-plane properties.

Quasi-interwoven lay-ups produced by the RDFP methodology present a potential method for creating preforms with layer connectivity and crimp. The RDFP carbon fibre preforms produced for this work were based on the Advanced Placed Ply (AP-Ply) structure, with pin spacing ranging from 2.5mm to 10mm. The narrowest pin spacing creates a cross-ply non-crimp preform whilst the widest spacing creates a quasi-interwoven composite upon consolidation, with high levels of layer crimp. Rectangular test coupons were cut according to the Queen Mary test protocol and subjected to low velocity impact and compression after impact testing. A distinguishable improvement in damage resistance was observed for the quasi-interwoven lay-up when compared with the non-crimp lay-up. Despite the high layer undulation levels seen with the quasi-interwoven lay-ups, these specimen have comparable compression after impact strengths to those with lower levels of undulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive, marine and aerospace industries, to name a few, are working to replace traditionally metal parts with lightweight composite alternatives, as already seen with BMW's "project i" cars with carbon fibre chassis. This is expected to drive an increase in demand for composite materials over the coming years, with there being no doubt about the advantages that fibre reinforced composites have over traditional structural materials. Their high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios make composites preferable in many instances, with their versatility in the design of stiffness and strength to match the specifications required by the application. Most composite preforms are produced through the stacking of 2D fabric layers or the placement of pre-impregnated tape layers onto a mould. These layups, when impacted or loaded in the out-of-plane direction, exhibit poor mechanical properties and delamination of the layers often occurs. As a result the structure becomes less able to withstand loading. This poor performance is due to a significant proportion of the load being carried by the matrix, rather than the fibres [1]. When delamination damage occurs the composite's in-plane mechanical properties degrade and thus their load bearing performance. The level of property degradation is indicative of the composite structure's damage tolerance.

Damage tolerance is defined as the material's ability to continue functioning after a damaging event [2], and is a design philosophy that was introduced during the 1970's for the design of aircraft structures. The classic methodology of assessing a composite structure's compressive strength after impact to determine damage tolerance may be largely influenced by the fact that the fuselage of an aircraft is subjected to significant compressive loading during flight. The typically poor damage

tolerance of composites is one of the main limiting factors when it comes to composite use for primary aircraft structures. It is well documented that low energy impacts can result in internal damage to the composite with minimal disruption to the surface and that this barely visible impact damage (BVID) can still cause significant loss of strength [3]. There are two main strategies for the improvement of a composite's damage tolerance: modification of the structure of reinforcement fibres or modification of the constituent materials [4]. Of particular interest are 3D fibrous preforms where fibres are placed or aligned in the z-axis, out-of-plane. One of the more popular methods is 3D weaving where binder tows, typically at a volume fraction of between 0.5% and 10% [5], are integrally woven between the layers as the fabric is manufactured. One mode I delamination study found that the interlaminar fracture toughness of a carbon 3D orthogonal woven composite increases by 10 times from crack initiation, where no through thickness reinforcement exists, to steady state propagation of the crack among the reinforcement [6].

2 QUASI-INTERWOVEN STRUCTURES

Advanced Placed Ply (AP-Ply) structures are an alternative lay-up structure with improved through-thickness properties. This structure was developed using robotic fibre placement by Nagelsmit [7]. These AP-Ply structures were manufactured using pre-impregnated fibres laid in such a way that there was a level of connectivity between the laminate's layers due to the induced fibre crimp. Despite the composite cross-section appearing similar to a woven structure, the architecture is not truly woven as the layers of fibrous tows are not interlaced. These structures are also, therefore, known as quasi-interwoven.

Figure 1: The bi-axial quasi-interwoven stacking sequence from A to D.

The method for producing a bi-axial AP-Ply structure can be seen in Figure 1, and is as follows:

- A. The first layer is formed by laying parallel tows in the 0° direction, interspersed by empty gaps.
- B. The second layer of fibres is placed in the 90° direction with the same spacing as layer 1.
- C. The third layer is placed in the 0° direction, between the tows of layer 1.
- D. The fourth layer is placed in the 90° direction, between the tows of layer 2.

Spacing the tows in the manner described above causes the tows to nest into the gaps below, forming layer crimp. The visual result of the layer settling with dry fibres can be seen in Figure 4. This crimping creates a level of layer connectivity that has been shown to improve the out-of-plane properties of pre-impregnated tow composites [7].

In the work carried out by Nagelsmit, pre-impregnated tows were placed using the Coriolis fibre placement system, capable of laying multiple tows simultaneously, maintaining the tow flatness and consolidating the preform in-situ using a heated end effector. In comparison, the architectures manufactured for this research were fabricated through the placement continuous dry fibre tow around pins on a board, using robotic dry fibre placement (RDFP). Once deposited, the dry tow loses its original flatness due to the curvature of the pins and the high modulus of the carbon fibres. This research looks in to whether the improvement of out-of-plane properties is still applicable and feasible when the quasi-interwoven structure is formed using RDFP technology.

3 MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

The cross-ply and quasi-interwoven structures produced for this research were manufactured using 12K Toray T700S carbon fibre spread tow. Three different panel configurations were chosen to investigate the effect of layer crimp on damage tolerance, with 2.5mm pin spacing being chosen to represent a cross-ply non-crimp fabric (NCF) and a 10mm spacing representing the maximum achievable crimp for a quasi-interwoven structure. A 5mm pin spacing was chosen to attempt to create a panel with low levels of quasi-interweave. The panel specifications for manufacture can be seen in Table 1.

Panel Nomenclature	Tow Size	Pin Spacing	Stacking Sequence
12K-2.5-(0/90) ₃	12K	2.5mm	[0/90] ₃
12K-5-(0/90) ₆	12K	5mm	[0/90] ₆
12K-10-(0/90) ₁₂ -1	12K	10mm	[0/90] ₁₂
12K-10-(0/90) ₁₂ -2	12K	10mm	[0/90] ₁₂

Table 1: Nomenclature for the manufactured panels

Using the pin spacing specifications, the quasi-interwoven panels are laid up as shown in Figure 1, with each layer consisting of one continuous 12K dry carbon fibre tow passed around perimeter pins. The pins are spaced in their rows according to the pin separation distance listed in Table 1. Non-crimp panels are laid up using the same RDFP technology, without the layer offset. A Festo 4-axis gantry machine with a custom fibre laying end effector is used for RDFP. The wrapping of the dry spread carbon tow around the pins in this manner causes a re-packaging of the tow, such that it is no longer flat. Figure 2 shows a 12k-10 panel after two layers have been placed, with the spacing between tows and non-flat tow structure visible.

Figure 2: The preform for 12K-10-(0/90)₁₂-1, showing the spacing between the tows to facilitate layer crimping.

The non-crimp and quasi-interwoven preforms were removed from the pin board prior to vacuum assisted resin infusion using a hot cure epoxy resin: Araldite LY564 and hardener Aradur 2954. Curing was carried out on a vacuum curing table over. Infused panels were then examined using a 5MHz C-scan probe before cutting to check for existing internal damage or faults.

3.1 Determination of Fibre Volume Fraction

It should be noted that each of the panels were designed such that the stacking sequence is balanced and that each panel contains approximately the same fibre content. That is, although the layer areal density varies between panel specifications, the overall preform areal density is consistent at 3.84kgm^{-2} . Using the preform areal density ($\rho_A=0.384\text{gcm}^{-2}$), fibre density ($\rho_f=1.80\text{gcm}^{-3}$) and composite thickness (t_c) the theoretical fibre volume fraction (FVF_t) is calculated using Equation 1.

$$FVF_t = \frac{\rho_A}{\rho_f} \times \frac{1}{t_c} \quad (1)$$

The resulting calculated values of FVF_t can be seen in Table 2. Composite thickness values were measured at 5 independent points on each coupon, with the values averaged for the entire panel. Due to the undulating surface of the preforms, particularly those with 10mm tow spacing, average thickness measurements are likely to be overestimated. These theoretical values were used to validate the FVF values measured using an adaptation of ASTM D3171-99 [8] burn-off methodology, as proposed by McDonough [9], whereby the samples are heated for 30 minutes at 600°C . This method is known to have an error margin of around 1% [9] due to the potential for incomplete resin burning or small levels of carbon fibre mass loss due to oxidation. Error levels are likely to be higher for FVF_t values due to the relationship of FVF_t to t_c . Experimental FVF (FVF_e) values will be used for normalisation calculations due to the know error level.

Panel ID	t_c (cm)	FVF_t	FVF_e
12K-2.5-(0/90) ₃	0.397	53.7%	56.6%
12K-5-(0/90) ₆	0.380	56.1%	59.1%
12K-10-(0/90) ₁₂ -1	0.452	47.2%	48.8%
12K-10-(0/90) ₁₂ -2	0.491	44.3%	48.1%

Table 2: Thickness values for calculation of FVF_t , FVF_e and the experimental FVF values (FVF_e).

3.2 Optical Cross-sectional Imaging of the Panels

The cross-sectional view of the panels (Figure 4) shows the fibre orientation within the composite. The RDFP technology employed for this research causes the flat spread carbon tows to repackage, no longer maintaining their intended flat structure. Instead the tow takes an elliptical shape. This is a potential reason for the low levels of fibre undulations seen in the 12k-2.5 cross-ply composite cross-section, with the upper tow nesting in the narrowest points where two ellipses meet.

Carbon tows were placed around pins at a 5mm spacing using the AP-Ply stacking sequence with the intention of creating a quasi-interwoven composite plate with low levels of layer crimp and therefore layer interconnectivity. Figure 3 indicates that this has not occurred for the 12k-5 samples, with the cross-section showing indiscernible tow crimp. It is likely that the 5mm spacing between pins and subsequent tow spacing was insufficient to allow layer nesting upon application of the vacuum bagging compressive forces for resin infusion. The tows have instead flattened, resulting in thinner, straight layers. In comparison the 12k-10 quasi-interwoven samples show layer crimp and connectivity due to the 10mm spacing being sufficient to allow layer nesting during composite forming compaction.

Figure 3: Cross-sectional views of the 12k-2.5-(0/90)₃, 12k-5-(0/90)₆ and 12k-10-(0/90)₁₂ panels.

4 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Rectangular test coupons measuring 89 x 55mm were cut from the manufactured panels, according to the Queen Mary test protocol [10]. Each panel set was shuffled and divided into 6 groups. Samples were subsequently mounted in an aluminum frame with a 40mm diameter opening and impacted over a range of energies using the instrumented drop-weight impact tester, Instron CEAST 9350. The mounted hemispherical impactor tip used had a 20mm diameter and a mass of 5.020kg. A minimum of 4 samples were impacted for each energy level. Post-impact damage width and shape was examined using a 5MHz C-scan probe.

Compression after impact (CAI) testing was carried out to evaluate the damage resistance and tolerance of the composites. Impacted coupons were mounted in the Queen Mary anti-buckling test rig and subjected to compressive loading at a rate of 0.5mm s⁻¹, until failure. Non-impacted samples were also tested to find the undamaged compressive strength.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Impact Testing and Damage C-Scan Imaging

The test coupons were impacted over a range of energies between 3J and 20J. For all impact energies, the resulting damage was non-penetrating. Many coupons at the lower energy range would also be considered to have BVID, with only a slight lightening of the surface at the impact site due to low levels of matrix-fibre debonding. Internal damage still exists, however. The damage projections can be seen from the C-scan images shown in Table 3.

It can be seen in Table 3 and Figure 4 that the damage propagation slows past the extent of the windowed area. The damage beyond this zone cannot therefore be taken to be fully representative of the composite. At energies of 5J or above, the 12k-2.5 coupons experience delaminations reaching the edge of the boundary. Near full delamination coverage of the windowed area occurs on the 8J impacted specimen. In comparison, the 12k-5 results show lower levels of delamination at the same energies, with full damage saturation not being seen until the 14J impacts. Saturation is not seen in the 12k-10 samples at any energy level, with samples impacted at 20J having an average damage width of 30.9mm. This is below the windowed threshold, as shown in Figure 4. Layer crimp has been shown to redirect and arrest delamination crack growth, along with the ability of crimped fibres to carry some of the impact load. A reduction in delamination area results.

Energy Level	12k-2.5	12k-5	12k-10
3J	E1		
5J	E6		
8J	E14		
14J	E17		
20J	E21		

Table 3: Typical C-scan images showing the damage levels for the 3 different panel lay-ups over the range of energies, with the red circle indicating the extent of the windowed area

Figure 4: The average damage widths of impacted coupons. The red line indicates the extent of the windowed area and error bars are one standard deviation in length.

Table 3 and Figure 4 show that the quasi-interwoven 12k-10 specimen have an improved damage resistance, with no evident damage on any of the 3J impacted coupons. This lack of damage indicates the ability of the layer interconnectivity and tow undulations to transfer the impact loading to the fibre rather than the matrix, as seen with woven fabrics in comparison to NCF.

In non-crimp preforms matrix cracking occurs upon impact, with the cracks following the layer fibre direction in multiple layers. Delamination initiates at the impacted site, spreading and constrained by the extent of the matrix cracking [11]. This creates the trapezoidal damage shape seen resulting from the lower energy impacts for both 12k-2.5 samples and 12k-5 samples prior to window saturation. In comparison, the 12k-10 sample damage area takes on a more circular shape, similar to damage growth in a composite with a woven preform. This circular shape occurs with woven fabrics due to the occurrence and intersection of both 0° and 90° fibres in each layer and therefore the growth of cracks in all directions. The appearance of a circular damage area for the 12k-10 impacted specimen therefore confirms that the induced layer crimp creates layer connectivity that allows the composite to transfer load in a similar manner to that in woven preform composites.

Figure 5: The force/time graphs and corresponding c-scan images for (a) 12k-2.5 samples and (b) 12k-10 quasi-interwoven samples .

Unidirectional and cross-ply composites experience a significant load drop during impact loading at the onset of damage, specifically delamination, whose value is independent of impact energy [12]. This behaviour can be seen in the force/time graphs for both 12k-2.5 coupons, Figure 5a. Similar

behaviour was observed for 12k-5 coupons. The force/time graph for the quasi-interwoven samples, 12k-10 (Figure 5b), show substantial load drops only on samples experiencing back face failure at the higher energy levels, as has also been seen in previous studies [13]. Other samples show only small load drops indicating progressive failure (8J), or a smooth curve indicating no or little damage (3J and 5J). This progressive failure behaviour points to the matrix damage mechanisms being unable to propagate freely, and is typical of woven fabrics.

5.2 Compression After Impact Testing

Ultimate compressive strength is proportional to fibre volume fraction. Therefore the measured values were normalised to a FVF of 50% using the value FVF_e to enable comparison between the panels. These FVF_e values can be found in Table 2. The normalised compressive strengths of impacted and non-impacted samples plotted against impact energy are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: A comparison between the normalised CAI strengths of different panel specifications.

The general trend for all is a steady decrease in normalised CAI strength with increasing impact energy, levelling out for the higher energies. This is due to damage being constrained at higher energies by the support window used during impact testing, as shown in Table 3, rather than a material property. The plateau between 0J and 3J for quasi-interwoven 12k-10 samples is a result of the increased damage resistance of the structure with the ability to remain undamaged at 3J impact loading. The CAI strength of the quasi-interwoven structure is then comparable to that of the cross-ply 12k-2.5 structure for the same impact energy. If only the fibrous structure of each panel is taken into consideration, this comparable CAI strength is unexpected. Composites containing non-crimp fibres, such as the cross-ply structures 12k-2.5, typically will outperform crimped structures under compression. This is due to the tow misalignment allowing for the early formation of micro-buckling and fibre kinking [5], resulting in matrix shearing and matrix shear failure at lower energy levels than with UD composites.

When the resin and fibre properties remain the same, a composite with smaller damage area will typically have an improved CAI strength when compared to one with a larger damage area. This effect is combined with the fibre crimp effect discussed above. The result is that the quasi-interwoven 12k-10 specimen exhibits a comparable CAI strength to the non-crimp cross-ply 12k-2.5 specimen, with a significantly less impact damage area for lower energies.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Of the samples produced using RDPF technology, only the 12k-10-(0/90)₁₂ showed the layer crimp and interconnectivity required for it to be classed as a quasi-interwoven composite. A 5mm pin separation was insufficient to produce this layer nesting, with the layers of the 12k-5-(0/90)₆ experiencing flattening instead. The 12k-2.5-(0/90)₃ panel can be considered to be a non-crimp cross-ply composite.

The tow undulations of the 12k-10 preform enables the fibres to carry some of the impact load. The layer connectivity allows this load to be passed between tow layers in a similar manner to composites consisting of woven preforms. This results in an increased damage resistance and damage initiation level. No damage is seen with a 3J impact, unlike with the cross-ply specimen. These 12k-10 samples have comparable CAI strengths to the 12k-2.5 cross-ply samples, despite having layer crimp which would normally reduce their compressive strengths.

7 REFERENCES

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